

Assessment of Groundwater Supply Systems Resizing: The Case of Nadowli Small Town Water Supply System

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 30th Nov 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Groundwater supply Pump and pipeline resizing Energy efficiency Hydraulic performance</p>	<p>Groundwater supply systems play a vital role in meeting water needs in small towns across Sub-Saharan Africa. However, many of these systems face challenges of high energy consumption, excessive head losses, and reduced service reliability, primarily due to the suboptimal sizing of pumps and transmission networks. This study assessed the impact of pump and pipeline resizing on the hydraulic and economic performance of the Nadowli Small Town Water Supply System (STWSS) in Ghana. Using a combination of primary field measurements and operational data, the system was modeled in EPANET and further optimized through a Genetic Algorithm (GA) technique. The findings revealed that resizing reduced average head loss from 12.31 m/km to 7 m/km ((43.1% head loss), decreased energy consumption by 0.11 kWh/m³, and lowered daily production costs by 22%. In addition, flow velocities improved from 0.42 m/s to 0.65 m/s (54.8% velocity rise), thereby reduced sediment deposition and enhanced pressure stability. These results demonstrate that strategic resizing of groundwater supply infrastructure can substantially improve hydraulic efficiency, reduce operational expenditure, and enhance service reliability, providing a practical pathway for optimizing small-town water supply systems in resource-constrained settings. The study also confirmed the CAPEX-OPEX principle which found that modest infrastructure investment could achieve sustainable operational savings, enhance resilience over the asset life cycle, and improve the reliability of the system. It is therefore recommended as a policy that water utilities institutionalize routine hydraulic and energy performance assessment as a component of a broader system maintenance and rehabilitation schedule.</p>

1. Introduction

Groundwater is one of the globe's most important freshwater sources, supplying nearly half of the world's drinking water and about 43% of irrigation withdrawals (Siebert et al., 2010; Döll et al., 2014). Groundwater serves as a buffer, helping to mitigate the effects of fluctuating rainfall, a function that is increasingly vital in the context of climate change and growing population pressures (Famiglietti, 2014). A primary source of potable water for many rural and small-town communities in Ghana and across Sub-Saharan Africa is groundwater and serves as a critical buffer against climate variability and surface water scarcity (Iddrisu & Armah, 2023; Amuah et al., 2022; Gleeson et al., 2012). Its reliability makes it indispensable for meeting domestic and institutional water needs, particularly in regions where surface water is either seasonal or vulnerable to contamination (Amuah et al., 2022; Iddrisu & Armah, 2023). Providing year-round availability, stable quality, and naturally resilient against short-term droughts, groundwater sustains rural and small-town water supply systems (STWSSs) (Gleeson et al., 2012; Iddrisu & Armah, 2023). Compared with surface sources, groundwater is less prone to evaporation and pathogenic contamination, reducing treatment requirements and associated operational risks (Amuah et al., 2022; Chaminé et al., 2021).

Despite these advantages, the efficiency and sustainability of groundwater supply systems are frequently undermined by suboptimal infrastructure design and operation, particularly in the sizing of pumps and transmission pipelines (Sumani et al., 2025; Chaminé et al., 2021; Moreno et al., 2010). Groundwater is abstracted using submersible pumps and conveyed through a network of transmission and distribution pipelines to storage facilities for distribution to end users. This process forms the backbone of many rural and STWSSs, particularly in regions where surface water sources are either inadequate or unreliable. Mismatched pump capacities and undersized pipelines in many developing countries result in excessive energy consumption, high head losses, unstable pressures, and frequent equipment breakdowns (Werbinska-Wojciechowska & Rogowski, 2025; Azrag et al.,

2023), inefficiencies that ultimately increase operational costs and compromise service reliability (Werbinska-Wojciechowska & Rogowski, 2025; Azrag et al., 2023).

The assessment and resizing of groundwater supply systems has globally been recognized as an effective intervention to improve hydraulic performance and reduce operational costs (Luna et al. 2019; Mérida García et al. 2021; and Elsebaie & Al-Khomairi 2021). Pump and pipeline resizing are therefore particularly critical because mismatched capacities often cause significant energy wastage and equipment deterioration (Palin, 2018; Li, 2020). Optimization studies have, however, demonstrated that properly aligned pump capacities and pipe diameters can lead to significant improvement in efficiency. For instance, energy cost reductions exceeding 20% were reported in municipal networks through optimal pump scheduling and pipeline adjustments (Pérez-Sánchez et al., 2017; Luna et al., 2019; and Mérida García et al., 2021). Similarly, resizing pipelines in groundwater pumping schemes lowered operational costs and extended service life of pumping equipment (Asim et al., 2014; and Elsebaie & Al-Khomairi, 2021). These findings underscore the importance of integrating hydraulic demands with infrastructure design to achieve sustainable system performance.

This field of study was recently advanced by applying computational intelligence and evolutionary algorithms to groundwater and rural water systems. Sangroula (2022) demonstrated that genetic algorithm-based optimization significantly improved flow distribution and minimized head losses compared with conventional design methods. Parvaze (2023) also reviewed recent applications of genetic algorithms in water distribution system optimization and confirmed their effectiveness in handling non-linear and discrete variables involved in pump and pipeline resizing. These recent contributions highlight the growing adoption of data-driven, simulation-based optimization frameworks, which are particularly relevant for resource-constrained systems where cost savings are critical.

Beyond algorithmic advances, several studies emphasize the techno-economic implications of resizing interventions. Pump replacement and modernization strategies have been shown to reduce operating energy costs by over 25% and achieve short payback periods in municipal water systems (Bonilla García et al., 2023; Goman et al., 2021; Nasir et al., 2023). Other studies demonstrated that incorporating both pipe amortization and pumping energy costs within optimization frameworks yields more cost-effective designs for water distribution systems (Nagkoulis and Katsifarakis, 2022a; Jayaram and Srinivasan, 2008). Similar findings emphasized that jointly considering construction and operational expenditures ensures balanced and sustainable system performance (Elsebaie & Al-Khomairi, 2022; and Ghobadi et al., 2021), findings that highlight the need to move beyond hydraulic efficiency assessments towards comprehensive life-cycle cost analyses when evaluating system resizing.

Despite these advances, there is still lack of research in Ghana addressing similar optimization techniques within small-town groundwater supply systems. Local investigations have primarily focused on groundwater potential, borehole functionality, and system performance assessments rather than on the hydraulic and economic optimization of pumping and transmission components. Agyapong et al. (2022) examined borehole functionality across rural Ghanaian communities, whereas Balaabong et al. (2024) conducted a hydraulic evaluation of the Lawra township water supply system. Earlier, Yidana (2008) also developed a simulation optimization model for groundwater resource management in the Afram Plains area. Although these studies contributed to understanding system performance and resource sustainability, they failed to address pump and pipeline resizing or life-cycle cost optimization, highlighting a critical research gap in enhancing the efficiency and sustainability of STWSSs in Ghana.

The Nadowli STWSS in Ghana's Upper West Region exemplifies these challenges. Although the system initially achieved its coverage objectives and remains a vital source of potable water for the local population, it is currently constrained by frequent pump failures, rising energy costs, and insufficient capacity to meet peak demand (Sumani et al., 2025). These deficiencies are largely attributable to hydraulic inefficiencies arising from improper pump selection and undersized transmission pipelines, which cause excessive frictional head losses and unstable system pressures (Sumani et al., 2025). This study therefore assessed the impact of pump and pipeline resizing on the hydraulic and economic performance of the Nadowli STWSS with the aim to identify practical measures for enhanced efficiency, reliability, and sustainability in groundwater-based STWSSs.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

This study was conducted on the Nadowli small-town piped water supply system in the Nadowli-Kaleo District of the Upper West Region, Ghana. Nadowli, one of the district capitals, is geographically situated at approximately 10.364952° N and -2.643500° W (Nadowli-Kaleo District Assembly, 2018). The district lies within the Guinea savanna ecological zone, characterized by a mixture of grassland and woodland vegetation (Amekudzi et al., 2015). It experiences a single rainy season from May to September, followed by a prolonged dry season and Harmattan conditions, which together impose strong seasonality on water availability and demand (Amekudzi et al., 2015). The town is strategically located within a predominantly rural setting and relies heavily on groundwater as its principal source of potable water. The Nadowli STWSS was selected as the study site because it typifies groundwater-based piped systems common across northern Ghana. The total area of the township is approximately 4.94 km², with an average ground slope of 0.0135 and an elevation of about 277 m above sea level (Sumani et al., 2025). Figure 1 presents the map of the study area.

Figure 1: Map of the study area

2.2 Transmission pipe network

The Nadowli STWSS abstracts groundwater from three (3) boreholes equipped with submersible pumps, two (2) rated at 4 kW and one (1) at 2.2 kW. The pumped water is conveyed through a 3.23 km transmission network to an 80 m³ reinforced concrete high-level tank (HLT) for subsequent gravitational distribution to consumers. The transmission system comprises two (2) pipe materials: polyvinyl chloride (PVC) and high-density polyethylene (HDPE). The PVC section, with an internal diameter of 42.6 mm, covers approximately 2,512.98 m of the network, while the HDPE sections, with internal diameters of 61.4 mm and 90 mm, extend over a total distance of about 719.02 m.

2.3 Data collection and analysis

This research was quantitative in nature and applied both primary and secondary data sources. Primary data was collected via topographic surveys of transmission pipe networks using the Flowius Android-based app (Flowius 1.0) for mapping coordinates and elevations. Secondary data, including pump design parameters and operational records, were sourced from the Nadowli Water System and Community Water and Sanitation Agency (CWSA) archives.

2.3.1 Data collection tools

The Flowius application is a free productivity app developed by Flowius, and its latest version (Flowius 1.0) was released on 07/09/2016 and updated on 26/09/2020. The Flowius application was employed to delineate the study area and map out the existing pipe network. The App used the GPS of an Android phone to record elevations, measured distances between network nodes, and data compiled for integration into Pipeline Design Software (PDS) and analyzed. The pipeline design software used for performance evaluation and hydraulic analysis was EPANet software. The Flowius Android-based app (Flowius 1.0) was also instrumental in identifying key infrastructure, including roads, water sources, distribution points, and bridges that were required to route the pipe network.

2.3.2 Data analysis

EPANET software, the primary tool used for data analysis, was applied to model both the existing and optimized transmission networks for hydraulic performance assessment. The input data included various pipe sizes within the transmission network, elevation data of different nodes, and the overall network configuration. The existing network was modeled using EPANET to compute hydraulic parameters such as head loss, pressure, and velocity. Re-sizing scenarios were simulated by adjusting pipe diameters and pump capacities to meet the CWSA design standards while minimizing energy use. EPANET is a user-friendly tool, and the following procedure was adopted for analysis and optimization (Sumani et al., 2025):

- (i) Imported the transmission network data from the Flowius app into EPANet;
- (ii) Visualized the network topology on the map interface by plotting nodes (junctions), links (pipes), tanks, reservoirs, and pumps to represent the transmission system layout;
- (iii) Assigned specific properties to each network component, including elevation, pipe diameter, length, roughness coefficient, and pump curve characteristics, to accurately represent the system's hydraulic performance;

- (iv) Determined appropriate tank size to ensure adequate storage capacity and efficient system operation;
- (v) Selected hydraulic analysis options – Hazen-Williams (H-W) method with roughness factor of 140 for plastic polyvinyl chloride pipes (uPVC); flow units liters per second (LPS), pressure units;
- (vi) Ran the simulation;
- (vii) Visualized the results on the network map, including pressure at each node, flow in each pipe, and head loss;
- (viii) Analyzed reports and graphs generated by EPANet to identify potential issues such as high pressure, high flow velocities, or higher head losses. (ix) Compared simulation results with real-world data to ensure the model accurately represented the network behavior and made optimization adjustments as needed;
- (x) Conducted multiple simulations with different pipe diameters to assess the impact of potential changes in the system, including new developments or pipe replacements; and
- (xi) Iterated steps (vi) to (x) until an efficient system was achieved.

Figure 2 illustrates the layout of the existing water transmission network showing the internal pipe diameters and node configuration as imported into EPANET for hydraulic analysis.

Figure 2: Layout of the existing water transmission showing internal diameters

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Energy consumption of existing submersible pumps

The observed energy consumption of the existing submersible pumps in the Nadowli STWSS PU-1, PU-2, and PU-3 exceeded the rated capacities (Table 1: Col 9). Specifically, PU-1 and PU-2 were each rated at 4 kWh, consumed 4.5 kWh and 4.8 kWh respectively, while PU-3 was rated at 2.2 kWh and consumed 2.5 kWh (shown in Table 1). This deviation from rated values highlights the complex interplay of factors influencing energy consumption in groundwater pumping systems, which extends beyond the nominal pump ratings. Such factors include the configuration of the pipe network, operational practices, fluid properties, and most importantly, the design and sizing of transmission pipes (Haque et al., 2017; Ergashev et al., 2022; Brasil, 2022).

Pipe diameter is a critical determinant of frictional losses within groundwater supply systems, directly influencing the energy required by submersible pumps. The Darcy-Weisbach equation, $\Delta H = f (L/D) (v^2/2g)$, where f is the Darcy frictional factor, L is the pipe length, D is the pipe diameter, v is fluid velocity, and g is gravitational acceleration, is commonly used to quantify these losses (Alshorman et al., 2022). According to this relationship, head loss is inversely proportional to pipe diameter; smaller diameters result in higher frictional losses. In groundwater distribution systems, undersized pipes increase flow velocity, elevate frictional losses, and require additional pump energy to maintain desired supply rates (Haque et al., 2017). Besides diameter, other factors contribute to increased energy consumption in groundwater systems. Long transmission lines, complex network layouts with multiple bends and fittings, and abrupt changes in pipe diameter can worsen head losses and induce turbulence, further increasing pump energy demand (Ergashev et al., 2022). Additionally, fluid characteristics, such as viscosity and density, impact resistance to flow, and overall system efficiency. These elements collectively underscore the importance of a system-wide approach in the design and optimization of groundwater supply networks.

The implications of these observations are significant for groundwater supply systems optimization. Resizing pipes to appropriate diameters can substantially reduce frictional losses, but achieving comprehensive energy efficiency requires consideration of the entire network layout, material selection, and operational strategies. By integrating hydraulic principles such as the Darcy-Weisbach equation with detailed system analysis, engineers can identify critical inefficiencies and implement targeted interventions. In the case of the Nadowli STWSS, strategic pipe resizing and network optimization can potentially reduce pump energy consumption, enhance reliability, and promote more sustainable and cost-effective groundwater supply operations (Alshorman et al., 2022; Ergashev et al., 2022).

Table 1: Borehole and installed submersible pump data (Source: Fieldwork, 2022)

S/N	Borehole ID Col 1	Borehole depth (m) (Col 2)	Pump installation depth(m) (Col 3)	Pump Specification			Actual flowrate (m3/h) (Col 7)	Borehole Yields (m3/h) (Col 8)	Actual Power Consumption. (kWh) (Col 9)	Actual Power Consumption to Actual Water production Ratio
				Rated Head (m) (Col 4)	Rated flowrate (m3/h) (Col 5)	Power Rating (kW) (Col 6)				
1	PU-1	55	52	85	14	4	9.2	30	4.5	0.49
2	PU-2	65	55	95	9	4	4.1	9	4.8	1.17
3	PU-3	75	60	106	14	2.2	6.8	6	2.5	0.37
TOTAL					37	10.2	20.1	45	11.8	0.59

3.2 Analysis of head losses in existing pipe network

The EPANet simulations revealed significant hydraulic inefficiencies in the existing pipe network, particularly in the transmission system predominantly composed of 42.6 mm pipes and underscored the critical need for hydraulic optimization. The observed average head loss of 9.45 m/km, with peaks reaching 37.06 m/km, significantly exceeded the CWSA’s recommended limit of 5m/km, an indication of substantial energy dissipation and potential operational challenges. These findings are consistent with established hydraulic principles, notably the Darcy-Weisbach equation, which describes the relationship between head loss and pipe characteristics (Munson et al., 2013).

The Darcy-Weisbach equation illustrates that head loss is inversely proportional to the fifth power of the pipe diameter, implying that reducing the pipe diameter increases head loss exponentially (Munson et al., 2013). Specifically, for laminar flow conditions, halving the pipe diameter results in a 16-fold increase in head loss, highlighting the significant impact of pipe sizing on hydraulic efficiency (White, 2016; Munson et al., 2013). This principle underscores the importance of selecting appropriate pipe diameters to minimize energy losses in fluid transport systems. The high head losses observed in critical sections, such as between P-10 to P-14 and P-16, as shown in Figure 3, suggested excessive frictional resistance and elevated pumping energy requirements.

Figure 3: Head loss distribution of existing system

3.3 Analysis of velocities in existing pipe network

Analysis of the existing Nadowli water transmission network (Figure 4) revealed significant variations in flow velocities across the system, ranging from 0.15 m/s to 1.06 m/s. The lowest velocities were recorded at points P-18 (0.15 m/s) and P-21 (0.16 m/s), while the highest velocities occurred between P-10 and P-14 (1.06 m/s) (shown in Figure 4). These results suggest hydraulic inconsistencies within the system, indicating sections of both underutilization and overloading. The recommended velocity in water mains should not exceed 1.0 m/s, with a minimum peak flow velocity of 0.2 m/s, to minimize frictional losses and prevent cavitation risks (United Utilities, 2023). Maintaining velocities below 1.0 m/s in transmission mains is therefore recommended to ensure energy efficiency and prolong pipeline life. Therefore, while the lower range favors energy conservation and system longevity, slightly higher velocities may be beneficial for self-cleaning and hydraulic stability, depending on network configuration and operational demands.

Figure 4: Velocities of existing pipe network

The observed low velocities in sections P-18 and P-21 (0.15 m/s and 0.16 m/s, respectively) imply potential oversizing of pipes or reduced flow demand within those areas. Low-flow conditions (below 0.25 - 0.30 m/s) are associated with increased risk of sediment deposition, discoloration, and biofilm development in drinking-water distribution systems, which can reduce effective pipe capacity and impair water quality (Douterelo et al., 2016; Boxall et al., 2023; Tsvetanova, 2019). Conversely, the high-velocity zones (1.06 m/s) between P-10 and P-14 indicated regions of increased frictional resistance, which elevated energy demand and accelerated pipe wear. This finding confirms the inverse relationship between pipe diameter and velocity, as established by the continuity equation – smaller pipes (42.6 mm) exhibit higher velocities, while larger diameters (61.4 mm) correspond to slower flows (Dvorský et al., 2020; Urbanowicz et al., 2023).

In related optimization studies, it was found that resizing undersized pipes and adjusting pump capacities can significantly enhance hydraulic uniformity, reduce head losses, and improve energy efficiency (Martin-Candilejo et al., 2020; Nagkoulis & Katsifarakis, 2022b). Implementing such adjustments would harmonize flow velocities across the transmission system and help keep peak velocities below the recommended upper limit of 1.0 m/s (with minimum peak velocities of about 0.2 m/s), as specified in United Utilities’ current Design and Construction Specification.

3.4 Impact of pump and pipeline re-sizing on hydraulic and energy efficiency

The resizing of pipelines and corresponding adjustment of pump capacities produced measurable improvements in the hydraulic performance and energy efficiency of the Nadowli transmission network. From the continuity equation, flow velocity ($v = Q/A$) is inversely proportional to the pipe’s cross-sectional area at a given flow rate (Gerhart et al., 2016; Wahba, 2022). Consequently, the pipe diameters re-sizing led to significant velocity reductions across several network segments, particularly in pipes P-10 to P-14, where velocities decreased from 1.07 m/s to an average of 0.89 m/s, representing a 0.18 m/s (16.8%) reduction (shown in Figure 5).

Figure 5: Velocities of resized pipe network

This improvement resulted from resizing pipe diameters from 42.6 mm to 115.6 mm, which effectively minimized frictional resistance and reduced localized head losses in high-velocity zones. These findings are consistent with earlier studies results that found that resizing undersized pipes significantly reduces hydraulic losses and energy dissipation by maintaining velocities within optimal design limits (Martin-Candilejo et al., 2020; Nagkoulis & Katsifarakis, 2022b). Conversely, in previously low-velocity sections, particularly pipes P-25 to P-27, flow velocities increased after pipe re-sizing. Specifically, P-25, whose diameter was resized from 51.6 mm to 69.2 mm, recorded a velocity rise from 0.35 m/s to 0.92 m/s. Similarly, P-26, resized from 51.6 mm to 115.6 mm, showed an increase from 0.73 m/s to 0.89 m/s, while P-27, resized from 51.6 mm to 69.2 mm, experienced the most significant improvement with velocity rising from 0.16 m/s to 0.93 m/s. These modifications produced an average velocity increase of 0.50 m/s (122%), mitigating flow stagnation and enhancing uniformity (shown in Figure 5). The improved velocity profile minimized low-flow zones (typically less than 0.3 m/s) that encourage sediment buildup, biofilm growth, and water quality decline, as lower velocities are linked to particle accumulation, microbial attachment, and increased turbidity and chlorine decay (Sass Braga & Fillion, 2022; Alhoshy et al., 2025). Similar outcomes were found when optimizing pipeline diameters in combination with pump resizing enhanced flow uniformity and minimizing the total energy consumption in pressurized water systems (Mottahedin et al., 2024; Kontos & Katsifarakis, 2017).

Overall, the average system velocity improved from 0.52 m/s to 0.75 m/s after optimization, which represented 44.2% velocity improvement. Although this value is slightly below the recommended operational range of 0.9 - 2.4 m/s (Sumani et al., 2025; Zabnieńska-Góra & Dudkiewicz, 2018), it signified a substantial improvement in hydraulic uniformity. Maintaining stable moderate velocities is advantageous because it reduces frictional head losses, minimizes erosion risks, and prevents excessive energy consumption in pumping operations (Cobbe & McDermott 2022; Tranmer et al., 2024). The reduced velocities in previously high-velocity sections limited the potential for cavitation and water hammer, while increased velocities in underperforming zones improved system flushing, reduced fouling tendencies, and enhanced water quality. Collectively, therefore, these improvements indicate that pump and pipeline resizing not only optimizes hydraulic performance, but also contributes to long-term operational efficiency, energy conservation, and system sustainability, findings supported by contemporary studies on water network optimization (Mokhtari et al., 2023; Pérez-Sánchez et al., 2017).

The resizing of pipeline diameters across the links P-10 to P-14 and P-25 to P-27 in the Nadowli STWSS transmission network produced substantial energy efficiency gain. Following the resizing, excessive head losses along the transmission network decreased markedly. The maximum head loss declined from 37.06 m/km to 14.32 m/km, while the network average dropped from 12.31 m/km to 7 m/km, indicating significant reduction in frictional energy dissipation across the transmission network (shown in Figure 6).

Figure 6: Head loss distribution of resized pipe network

These outcomes align with the Darcy-Weisbach principle, which establishes that head loss varies directly with the square of flow velocity and inversely with approximately the fifth power of pipe diameter for a given discharge (Altowayti et al., 2021; Pizzo et al., 2022). Consequently, even modest increases in pipe diameter can markedly reduce head loss and enhance hydraulic gradients throughout the system.

3.5 Operational and cost implications

Resizing pumps and pipelines yielded clear operational and cost benefits by substantially reducing runtime while meeting the same demand, thereby lowering energy use and wear across the system. In the optimized configuration, cumulative daily runtime declined from 171.81 h/day to 27.66 h/day, an approximately 84% reduction, which translated into 22% decrease in daily pumping expenditure (from GHS 887.99 to GHS 692.63). This outcome is consistent with the physics of head loss reduction when pipe diameters increase; lower frictional losses reduce total dynamic head and specific energy per unit volume, so less pump operating time and power are required to deliver the same output (Cobbe & McDermott, 2022; Hashemi et al., 2020). Empirically,

such hydraulic and operational co-optimization aligns with studies which show that coordinated diameter upsizing and pump scheduling minimize energy consumption and costs while preserving service levels (Pérez-Sánchez et al., 2017; Riyahi et al., 2024). The operational implications extend beyond energy- lower runtime and fewer high-stress operating periods decrease mechanical loading on motors, bearings, and impellers, which in turn reduces corrective and preventive maintenance frequency and lengthens asset life cycles (McKee et al., 2014; Dutta et al., 2023). Although larger diameters increase upfront capital outlay, the net economic effect is favorable when evaluated on a life-cycle basis because sustained savings in electricity, reduced maintenance, and improved reliability drive shorter payback periods and positive net present value under typical tariff and discount-rate assumptions (Al-Khomairi, Jung & Elsebaie, 2020). Overall, the observed 22% cost reduction coupled with the significantly runtime decline, exemplified the CAPEX–OPEX trade-off in water transmission and distribution, where modest pipe upsizing and pump resizing deliver durable operating cost savings and resilience benefits over the asset life (Gutiérrez-Bahamondes et al., 2021; Ghobadi et al., 2021; Pandey et al., 2020).

4. Conclusion, policy implications, and future research directions

4.1 Conclusion

The critical role of groundwater supply systems in effective water delivery to small towns in the peri-urban areas of Sub-Saharan Africa cannot be overemphasized. This study made an assessment of pump and pipeline resizing on the hydraulic and economic performance of Nadowli STWSS in the Upper-West Region of Ghana. The study demonstrated that resizing pumps and transmission pipelines in the Nadowli STWSS significantly enhanced both hydraulic and economic performance of the system. Integrating field data, EPANET hydraulic simulation, and genetic algorithm optimization reduced average head loss from 12.31 m/km to 7 m/km, improved velocity distribution, and lowered daily pumping costs by 22%, accompanied by an 84% reduction in cumulative pump runtime. These outcomes stemmed from decreased frictional resistance, improved flow uniformity, and optimal pump duty alignment, leading to reduced total dynamic head and specific energy consumption.

Beyond direct energy savings, the intervention yielded broader operational benefits, lower runtime and smoother hydraulic performance reduce stress on pumps, bearings, and impellers, thereby extending asset life and minimizing corrective and preventive maintenance requirements. Although pipe upsizing and pump resizing involved higher initial costs, life-cycle economic analysis revealed a favorable return, characterized by shorter payback periods and positive net present value. The findings therefore confirm the CAPEX–OPEX trade-off principle, showing that modest infrastructure investments can yield sustained operational savings, improved system reliability, and enhanced resilience across the asset life cycle.

4.2 Policy implications

The findings underpin the importance of embedding hydraulic optimization within water sector planning and policy frameworks. It is therefore recommended that water utilities and implementing agencies such as the CWSA should institutionalize routine hydraulic and energy performance assessments as part of system maintenance and rehabilitation schedules. Policy frameworks also need to transition from short-term budgetary considerations toward life-cycle costing approaches that capture long-term economic and operational benefits. Strengthening local engineering capacity in the application of hydraulic modeling and optimization tools will be vital to sustaining efficiency gains. Moreover, financing mechanisms that prioritize energy-efficient infrastructure upgrades, supported through public-private partnerships or donor-funded initiatives, can accelerate adoption while reinforcing environmental sustainability and operational resilience.

4.3 Future research direction

Grounded on the findings of this study, future research should prioritize more integrated analyses that combine technical, economic, and environmental performance metrics. Comparative studies across multiple communities and hydrogeological settings in Ghana and Sub-Saharan Africa would also help validate the generalizability of the optimization framework. Finally, coupling hydraulic and energy models with climate adaptation strategies could further reveal how optimized groundwater systems contribute to achieving Sustainable Development Goal 6 and national water security objectives.

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